

ViSS

ViSS Preliminary Residues Management Plan / D1.2

WP1, T1.2

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2. List of abbreviations

BFRs	bone and feather residues
BHFs	bone and feathers hydrosylates
COD	chemical oxygen demand
DoA	description of the action
PHBV	poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)
SSbD	safe and sustainable by design
VFAs	volatile fatty acids

3. Executive summary <abstract>

In the ViSS project, the production of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate), also called PHBV, will be accomplished using residues from the candy and poultry industries as feedstock. These residues are rich in organic matter which makes them susceptible to decomposition. To ensure the development of a reliable production method, the physicochemical composition of the feedstock needs to be similar over the production step. In this context, a residue management plan has been done to minimise issues coming from inhomogeneities in the residues during the project and to ensure an appropriate delivery thereof.

This deliverable, D1.2, is a public document from the ViSS project, "Viable, safe and sustainable PHBV value chain for food packaging applications." The project runs for 48 months, from September 2023 to August 2027.

The main objective of this plan is to outline the management of residues from the sugar and poultry industries that will be used as feedstock to produce poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate), or PHBV. These residues are rich in organic matter and susceptible to decomposition, so a management plan is crucial to ensure a consistent physicochemical composition for a reliable production method.

The deliverable, which was due on November 30, 2023, was submitted on March 6, 2024, because of a delay. In the updated version (v2.0, submitted on September 2025) of the deliverable, we have provided a justification for this delay in line with EC recommendations. The delay was primarily caused by two factors:

- First, some additional analysis carried out to the residues. Additional analysis was performed on the residues because the initial data provided by the candy residue supplier, VIDAL, showed significant fluctuations in their chemical composition. The project partners (CETBIO and IRIS) needed more detailed information to validate the sugar residues as "true carbon sources" for their biotechnological processes. To address this, eight additional samples were collected from VIDAL facilities over a week and analysed. The results of this new analysis showed that the total sugar content was significantly lower than expected. The heterogeneity of the residues confirmed by these additional analyses is a major challenge.
- Second, no sufficient involvement of the task leader, VIDAL. Consequently, CETEC, as WP leader, assumed the responsibility of elaborating the deliverable.

4. Results and discussion

As described in the DoA and more recently in deliverable D.1.1, residues coming from the candy and poultry industries will be used as feedstock for the production of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate), also known as PHBV, with high mol content in the monomer 3-hydroxyvalerate (3-HV). Due to the inherent nature of these residues, it is important to draw a management plan to avoid undesired degradation processes that might hinder the revaluation of these waste materials.

Figure 1 depicts the flow of residues in the ViSS project. Waste from the candy industry will be supplied to CETBIO and IRIS. CETBIO will use these residues as carbon sources for the production of PHBV and IRIS will turn them into volatile fatty acids VFAs (propionic and valeric acid). Concurrently, INPRALS (TCA third party) will provide CETEC with poultry residues to be hydrolysed before being incorporated into the PHBV production process.

Figure 1. ViSS residue flow diagram.

4.1. Collection and transportation

Despite a full physicochemical characterization of the residues will be made before being used as feedstock in the production of PHBV, it is important to understand how they are collected.

4.1.1. Collection of candies' sugar residues (VIDAL)

VIDAL, within the continuous environmental improvement program, has implemented the appropriate methodology and practices to define environmental objectives and targets and evaluate the degree of compliance. Among them is the minimisation of the production and discharge of sewage that is not admissible in the Municipal Ordinance of Molina de Segura (Spain). Based on the premise that it is possible to reduce discharge flows and concentrations of organic matter, the validity of the cleaning and elimination methods followed and the correct functioning of equipment and installations capable of generating

some contaminations of the discharge water have been questioned and re-evaluated over the last 15 years. On the basis of this reassessment, the "Sewage Minimisation Plan" was initiated, proceeding as a precautionary measure to close all the company's internal drainage and discharge points where water with high COD levels was being discharged, installing at the same time extraction/pumping systems for the collection of cleaning water from equipment and machinery in tanks in order to be able to carry out the relevant controls and measures aimed at identifying and characterising each of the aforementioned points. From there, the minimum non-recoverable water flows were stored until they were removed by authorised industrial wastewater managers. There are annual plans that emphasise the reduction of non-recoverable water production, but we cannot aspire to zero waste and there are certain volumes that we produce and that we have to manage with authorised managers.

As a result of the production process and the cleaning operations that are generated afterward, VIDAL generates an effluent that is not recoverable, and which is currently being managed externally with authorised wastewater managers. The waters that make up the non-recoverable effluent are classified according to their origin, although they are all collected and mixed in the same tanks to facilitate external management by the managers at the end of the process.

All these volumes are stored in 25 m³ tanks at room temperature until they are removed by the waste manager (***ViSS partners in this case***). They are stored for a maximum of 24 hours, and no control of parameters is conducted during the storage.

4.1.2. Collection of poultry residues (INPRALS)

No information has been provided by the supplier yet.

4.1.3. Residue transportation

Since all the residues involved contain high amounts of organic matter, they are prone to decompose. To maintain their physicochemical properties, the residues (VIDAL and ANPRILS residues) will be transported to IRIS, CETBIO, and CETEC *frozen* (preferably) or *refrigerated*. This will reduce the reaction rate of any biological or chemical process that could compromise the stability of the waste.

4.2. Residue management plan

The management plan described below will apply to all the residues independently of their nature.

4.2.1. Residue preservation (Storage)

For the first research trials, VIDAL will send to CETBIO and IRIS four samples recovered from its residual tank over four days (one sample per day). The delivered residues will be preserved at -20 °C in a separate freezer. Different tests will be carried out by CETBIO and IRIS to establish the best methodology for the use of VIDAL residues as a carbon source in fermentation and VFAs production, respectively.

The poultry hydrolysate produced by CETEC will also be preserved at -20 °C in a separate freezer until its use.

4.2.2. Sample stability and valorisation

For the development of the research experiments, the samples will be first thawed in a water bath to accelerate the defrosting process and avoid microbial contamination. The samples that have been frozen and thawed should never be refrozen.

Before any valorisation test, the four initial samples received from VIDAL will be thawed following the procedure described to analyse the samples' stability across time. To this end, the samples will be maintained for five days at room temperature on the laboratory bench. The sample's stability will be monitored by microbial growth (microscopy observation and plate count) and glucose concentration, which will be determined colourimetrically by the dinitrosalicylic method.

The residues' stability tests are crucial to developing a scalable storage plan, that is, avoiding the refrigeration of the waste. This is important since the refrigeration of high amounts of waste would imply an extra step in the process, contrary to the safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) concept.

For the valorisation research trials, different approaches will be assessed:

- The residues will be used directly without any pretreatment step.
- The residues will be firstly autoclaved at 121 °C for 20 min to sterilise before their use in the fermentation.
- The residues will be subjected to 0.22 µm filtration for sterilisation.

4.3. Waste management plan for bio-fermentation processes

Besides the definition of a management plan for the residues of the candy and poultry industries, the handling and management of the waste produced during the bioprocesses carried out by CETEC and IRIS was considered.

This procedure describes the standard methodology for removal and management of waste produced derived from Research Tasks, in the frame of the ViSS project (GA: 101081931) including general waste and specific laboratory waste (reagents and chemicals derived from laboratory work) hazardous or non-hazardous.

4.3.1. Responsibilities

All laboratory staff is responsible for complying with this procedure to ensure the safe and effective management of waste. The ultimate responsible for managing the specific laboratory waste, including hazardous chemicals and reagents derived from Research tasks is the Laboratory Responsible. This specific waste must be sent to a specific Waste Management company authorised by the Public Administration.

4.3.2. Consideration

All the partners are committed to recycling and reusing waste products whenever possible to produce an effective waste management system that maximises the conservation of natural resources and minimises environmental harm.

4.3.3. Associate documentation

- CE 1907/2006 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 18 December 2006. concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), establishing a European Chemicals Agency, amending Directive 1999/45/EC and repealing Council Regulation (EEC) No 793/93 and Commission Regulation (EC) No 1488/94 as well as Council Directive 76/769/EEC and Commission Directives 91/155/EEC, 93/67/EEC, 93/105/EC and 2000/21/EC.
- NTP 276: Eliminación de residuos en el laboratorio: Procedimientos generales. Nota Técnica de prevención.
- EUROPEAN WASTE CATALOGUE AND HAZARDOUS WASTE LIST.
- RD-180/2015, 13th of March concerning the procedure to transport waste products inside Spanish territory.
- Manual de gestió de residus industrials a Catalunya (Catalan Government).
Catàleg de residus de Catalunya (apply to IRIS).

4.3.4. Procedure

To develop effective and correct laboratory waste management, laboratory waste must be classified in order to receive the appropriate waste management procedure.

4.3.4.1. Hazardous chemical waste

Chemicals and reagents derived from laboratory work must be segregated adequately in different containers and must be sent to a specific company to be managed. These products only can be handled by trained staff using appropriate personal protective equipment. Label all containers with the group name from the chemical waste category and an itemized list of the contents. For example, do not label a container simply 'Corrosive Liquids'. List each chemical in the container, including all solvents used. List by full name only. Abbreviations, initials, or chemical formulas are not acceptable.

4.3.4.2. Bio-hazardous waste management

Microorganisms or other materials used in microbiological assays must be sterilized before throwing them. The sterilization procedure will be achieved with the autoclave equipment in appropriate receptacles and containers. The recommended setup for waste material is 123 °C for 24 minutes. Sterile material can be disposed of in the general waste container.

4.3.4.3. Waste store conditions

Waste disposed to be managed by the external waste management company should be stored in optimal conditions until processed (Room temperature, dry conditions). Store the waste in appropriate containers in a suitable area whilst awaiting collection.

4.3.5. Health and safety

Use laboratory coats, gloves, and safety glasses to manage chemical products. To avoid accidents, never transfer waste from one container to another.

4.4. Residue delivery plan

To avoid delays and ensure the timely completion of the goals established within ViSS project, a delivery plan of the residues used directly or indirectly in the production of PHBV has been developed.

4.4.1. VFAs production by IRIS

As it is well-described in the DoA, the production of 3-HV enriched PHBV needs the use of synthetic precursors such as propionic and valeric acid (referred to as VFAs). Within the ViSS project, a biotechnological approach for their production using candy residues has been envisaged. Table 1 gathers the estimation of the residue that IRIS will need during the first year project to ensure the realisation of milestone 4.

Table 1. Estimation of the amount of candy residues for the production of VFAs (propionic and valeric acid) during the first year of the project.

PHBV (Kg) Milestone 4	Candy Residue (L)
100	505 ± 83

4.4.2. PHBV production by CETBIO

The development of a reliable and reproducible methodology for the production of PHBV implies exhaustive control over the parameters that govern the fermentation process. Among them, the physicochemical composition of the culture media is of crucial importance.

Candy residues: carbon source

The ViSS project proposes the use of residues from the candy industry as a prospective carbon source for the biotechnological production of PHBV. The candy residue composition provided by the partner VIDAL is gathered in Table 2. As it can be observed, the residue is subjected to significant fluctuations in chemical composition, an undesired scenario that needs to be addressed.

Table 2. Physicochemical analysis of the candy residues provided by VIDAL.

Parameter	Average	Max.	Min.
<i>Alkalinity (mg/L)</i>	< 3	< 3	< 3
<i>pH (20 °C)</i>	3	4	3
<i>Salinity (g/L)</i>	1	1	1
<i>Conductivity (µS/cm, 25 °C)</i>	1774	2700	1100
<i>TSS (g/L)</i>	14.71	79.80	1.38
<i>VSS (g/L)</i>	14.35	73.99	1.36
<i>Toxicity (TU)</i>	42	399	6
<i>BOD (gO₂/L)</i>	61.16	149.14	30.81
<i>COD (gO₂/L)</i>	124.88	288.20	77.38
<i>COD_{filtered} (g/L)</i>	117.07	270.90	76.06
<i>Calcium (mg/L)</i>	77	110	35
<i>Ammonium (mg/L)</i>	1.24	4.50	0.07
<i>Nitrates (mg/L)</i>	1.81	2.80	1.10
<i>Total Nitrogen (mg/L)</i>	620	1328	150
<i>Phosphates (mg/L)</i>	10	22	2
<i>Total Phosphorous (mg/L)</i>	8	30	4
<i>Sulphites (mg/L)</i>	< 20	< 20	< 10
<i>Sulphate (mg/L)</i>	160	260	34
<i>Oils and fats (mg/L)</i>	159	1100.0	21.1
<i>Degrees Brix (°Bx)</i> or <i>Total sugars (% w/w)</i>	10	13	7

TTS: total suspended solids; **VSS:** volatile suspended solids; **Toxicity (TU):** Toxic Units; **BDO:** biochemical oxygen demand; **COD:** chemical oxygen demand; **COD_{filtered}:** chemical oxygen demand of the filtered residue.

Despite the detailed analytical profile provided by VIDAL, additional information was demanded by CETBIO and IRIS (as described in deliverable 1.1). Specifically, they were interested in the quantification of the most important mono- and disaccharides, since they are considered as the true carbon sources in their biotechnological processes. In this context, eight different samples were collected over a week at VIDAL facilities and their composition (average) is reported in Table 3. The measured amount of total sugars (2.91 ± 0.48 g/100 g residue) was significantly lower than the reported initially by VIDAL (7-13 g/100 g residue). Additionally, from the data in Table 2, the heterogeneity of the residues can be confirmed. This aspect might be a hurdle towards the development of a consistent and reproducible method for the production of PHBV since it would imply the thorough analysis of each residue batch before their use to maintain constant the composition of the fermentation media. The need to analyse each residue batch, apart from being costly and time-consuming, would bring the necessity of keeping the residues refrigerated or frozen until they are used as feedstocks to minimise intrinsic fermentation processes. This may be difficult when handling with big amounts of residues, as is expected.

In a nutshell, the employment of the current candy residues will imply research at a lab scale prior to the pilot-scale production of PHBV. It should be noted that other residues are being considered as an alternative to the candy residues.

Table 3. Average composition of the eight independent samples collected at VIDAL facilities.

Parameter	Values in % (w/w) (Mean \pm SD)
Fructose	1.12 \pm 0.32
Galactose	< 0.1*
Glucose	0.49 \pm 0.18
Lactose	< 0.1*
Maltose	0.68 \pm 0.14
Sucrose	0.64 \pm 0.47
Total sugars	2.91 \pm 0.48
Nitrates (NO_3^-)	4.29 \pm 3.69
Ammonium (NH_4^+)	< 0.25*
Total nitrogen	707.50 \pm 128.43
Phosphate (PO_4^{3-})	55.63 \pm 28.50
Total phosphorous	17.96 \pm 8.99

Based on the chemical composition of the candy residues, an estimation of the amounts necessary to achieve milestone 4 (first-year PHBV production, 2.3 Kg of PHBV per week) has been carried out using the data from Table 3. Two different scenarios have been considered in terms of PHBV production yield (2.0 and 3.0 g/L) where the concentration of glucose is maintained constant at 10 g/L. The estimation has been made using the total sugar concentration since, in principle, the microorganism involved in the production of PHBV can use a wide array of saccharides apart from glucose as carbon source.

Table 4. Estimation of the amount of candy residues for the production of PHBV during the first year of the project (milestone 4).

Scenario	PHBV production yield (g/L)	[Glucose] (g/L)	Candy Residue (L)
1	2.0	10	395.2 \pm 56.0
2	3.0	10	263.5 \pm 37.3

Poultry residues: nitrogen and phosphorous sources

Poultry residues will be used as a complementary nitrogen and phosphorous source for the production of PHBV. Before they can be effectively implemented in the process, they need to be submitted to a hydrolysis step. Indeed, the real source used during the fermentation process is referred to as *poultry bones & feathers residue hydrolysate (BFH)*. Due to the necessity of chemical pretreatment of the residues and the inherent heterogeneity thereof, fluctuations in the hydrolysate composition are expected. This will imply a physicochemical characterisation of the more important components before being used in the PHBV

production process. Table 5 gathers the chemical composition of the water-soluble fraction of two poultry residues provided by INPRALS. It should be noted that only the water-soluble part of the residue will be used in the fermentation process.

Table 5. Physicochemical profiles of the poultry residues provided by INPRALS.

Residue	TKN (%)	NH ₄ ⁺ (mg/Kg)	NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/Kg)	Total Phosphorus (mg/100g)
Decanter Pollo	0.1	87.8	<10	18.7
Decanter Cocido	0.1	47.3	<10	14.6

TKN: Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (organic and inorganic forms of nitrogen; The symbol “<” indicates the detection limit of the analytical method).

Even though the hydrolysis step will increase the concentration of soluble species, the estimation of poultry residues necessary for the production of PHBV during the first year of the project has been done with the data in Table 5. Thus, the values gathered in Table 6 describe the worst scenario possible: the maximum amount of poultry residue needed. Certainly, the hydrolysis step will reduce significantly the residue quantities to fulfill the fermentation requirements but an estimation based on the poultry hydrolysates would be inaccurate due to the reasons aforementioned.

Based on the chemical composition of the poultry residues, an estimation of the quantities necessary to fulfil the goals reported in milestone 4 has been carried out (Table 6). Two different scenarios have been considered in terms of PHBV production yield (2.0 and 3.0 g/L) where the concentration of total nitrogen and total phosphorous is maintained constant at 1.2 and 0.023 g/L, respectively. A clear issue is observed when looking carefully at the chemical composition of the residues supplied by INPRALS. A mismatch in the nitrogen/phosphorous ratio between the ideal fermentation conditions and the residue is observed (52.17 and 5.34, respectively). That means that nitrogen and phosphorous fermentation concentrations cannot be achieved by using only these poultry residues. The estimation made in Table 6 has been done focusing only on the phosphorus component (limiting reagent). If so, the external addition of nitrogen species will be needed to achieve the necessary nitrogen concentration for the biotechnological method to work correctly.

Table 6. Estimation of the amount of poultry residues for the production of PHBV during the first year of the project (milestone 4).

Scenario	PHBV production yield (g/L)	[Nitrogen] (g/L)	[Phosphorous] (g/L)	Poultry Residue (Kg)
1	2.0	1.2	0.023	4.36 - 5.57
2	3.0	1.2	0.023	2.90 - 3.71

5. Conclusions

A management plan for the feedstock to be used in the production of PHBV (residues from the candy and poultry industries) has been prepared. To guarantee the physiochemical stability of the feedstock during the process, they should be refrigerated (or frozen if possible) during their transportation and storage. This strategy will be used during the initial tests carried out at the lab scale. Additionally, the stability of the residues at ambient conditions will be also investigated. Moreover, a management plan for the waste produced during the processes involved in the production of PHBV and treatment of the candy and poultry residues (tasks 1.3.2 and 2.1.1., respectively) has been elaborated.

Finally, an estimation of the residues (candy and poultry) to be used by IRIS and CETBIO has been done for the first year of the project. It should be noted that the suitability of the delivered residues (candy and poultry) to be used as feedstock for the production of PHBV has been put under question and mitigation measures are being considered.